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New electromobility concepts: car-sharing service pilot test in Vigo

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Short Abstract

European cities are progressively shifting to sustainable mobility through the implementation of new models, supported over ICT applications. Remarkable examples are car-sharing schemes with electric vehicles (EV). In Vigo (Spain), a mid-size city in the northwest Spain, an electromobility pilot test is being carried out within the framework of the MOBI.Europe project, which purpose is to show the potential of integrated and interoperable ICT applications for electromobility in Europe. This pilot has special features due to the car-sharing service using parking facilities and the characteristics of the city itself. This paper describes the definition, planning and implementation of the electromobility pilot experience in Vigo, as well as the first results achieved and the conclusions drawn so far.

1 Introduction

The demonstration project MOBI.Europe, funded by the CIP programme, integrates trials developed in Vigo (Spain), Ireland, Portugal and the Netherlands, with the objective of showing the opportunities of ICT services associated with electromobility, defining, among other tasks, a common set of indicators to measure the impact of ICT solutions applied to transport. The project also addresses the problem of interoperability. For instance, in the case of the pilot test in Vigo, given the proximity of the Portuguese border, it must be ensured that EV users will be able to charge their electric vehicles regardless of which side of the border they are (roaming).

Car-sharing schemes allow users to rent EV for a limited time, and emerged as a creative solution to improve urban mobility in order to face traffic congestion in city centres and pollution associated with vehicle emissions. However, the use of EV involves additional difficulties, notably the availability of the charging. Also, car-sharing service is useful for occasionally car users, or for urban commuting trips.

Local, regional and national governments, as well as the European Commission, have launched a number of programs to promote and foster the development and use of EV. MOBI.Europe pilot in Vigo tests a car-sharing service integrated in public parkings supported by ICT systems.

2 City of Vigo

Vigo is a coastal city located in Galicia, near 35 km from the Portuguese border. It is the most populated city in the region. Including its metropolitan area, the number of inhabitants reaches 480.000 people. Vigo is also the industrial engine of the region, where automotive, shipbuilding and canning industries stand above all.

The city transport system lacks services available in larger cities (underground, tramways, bike-sharing, etc.), and is mainly based on the use of private vehicles, resulting in very heavy traffic, especially at peak times; and the unavailability of surface parking spaces. Urban public transport is reduced to taxis and buses.

3 Pilot test concept

Unlike other cities, where charging stations are installed on the street, the deployment of the charging network in Vigo has begun in underground parking areas. In this way, some car park facilities include specific EV slots equipped with charging points. Through ICT applications, users enjoy a more efficient parking experience by allowing them to remotely check parking availability, make parking reservations in advance and effectuate payment through remote RFID card.

Figure 1: EV parking slot

It is notable that the first units of the car-sharing fleet are Renault Twizy, a model that poses new mobility habits to drivers, differentiating vehicles able to perform long trips to this EV, suitable to congested traffic cities.

Figure 2: Car-sharing scheme

Also, a platform has been developed, comprising a web interface, registration system and database for implementing remote vehicle booking, pick-up, location, control and charging.

Figure 3: Web interface snapshot

4 First results and conclusions

MOBI.Europe stands from January 2012 to December 2014. Test is under execution, and therefore no definitive conclusions can be drawn. Nevertheless, some interesting hints may be shown.

Table1: Pilot test indicators September – December 2012

Concept	Value
EV	6
Users	53
Charging operations	190
Road mileage (Km)	4.114

Car-sharing has success potential, but it will depend on critical factors: availability of vehicles with certain characteristics, identification of preferred uses of EV (commuting or recreational use), users' profile, and the extent of ICT technologies, enabling booking regardless of the user's location. The fact of not having to find a parking space is one of the most valued features as well.

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